

BENEFITS OF E-LEARNING AND MOBILE SMART LEARNING IN LANGUAGE TEACHING**Temirkulova A.B.***master's degree student,**Al Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Kazakhstan***Abstract**

Education is crucial in life, and it has become available today due to new technologies. Among other things, it is vital to note the trend of learning foreign languages, globalization in the world has eliminated all kinds of borders and demand for learning them is growing every year.

It is worth noting that this opens the way for teachers of foreign languages. An important job in the field of teaching is intercultural communication, as it is said that students need to build communication with other people through language and culture. The teacher must not only know the language structure, but also knowledge of intercultural communication, which in the future will help students to build conversations with foreigners without obstacles and conflicts. Along with this, modern teaching requires knowledge of information technology. Global pandemic has dramatically transformed traditional education to distance learning. It is crucial for teachers to understand the different kinds of online learning, its benefits in education and some disadvantages.

In the field of education, the integration of technology in educational activities leads to the emergence of new terms that many people may confuse. In some cases, they may be similar in operation, have the same principle of operation, but also have some differences. The aim of this article to show the differences and similarities in the different kinds of online learning: such as m-learning, e-learning. A survey is conducted among students and teachers to assess the knowledge of the types of online learning in order to have an idea of how successful the integration of IT into education has been, and whether teachers use it in practice. Practical importance of research: The materials of this work can be used in educational work. It is also possible to use results of the research for statistics, and search ways and methods that will help improve the usefulness or effectiveness of using in practice types of technological ways of learning.

Keywords: smart technologies, language teaching, integration, IT, language, apps, e-learning, m-learning, d-learning.

Introduction

Globalization in the world strengthens integration processes that have a huge impact on the social, political and economic structure of the world of the new millennium, closely related to global innovative technologies. With the development of information and communications technology (ICT), overcoming problems while continuing education has become accessible during the pandemic. There is no doubt that due to the unified information intellectual educational environment, persons interested in acquiring knowledge already interact virtually, stimulating the development of electronic, distance, and mobile education. Consequently, global pandemic situation in 2020 is the beginning of a massive merger of teaching with modern technologies in the field of education.

Nowadays, active growth of online technologies has led to the fact that various types of online education and teaching have become available. For some people the following types of different technological ways of learning as m-learning, d-learning, e-learning, smart education might be incomprehensible, since they are all closely related. Most of the terms related to e-education such as (online learning), (open learning), (web learning), (computer-mediated learning), (blended learning), (mobile learning) involve the use of a computer or mobile device connected to the Internet, which makes it available to study anywhere, at any time, in any rhythm, by any means [6]. Among the various types of online learning mentioned above, the article discusses e-learning and m-learning and their advantages in teaching a

foreign language, above all let us consider the difference between the terms of technological ways of learning.

The first application of distance learning technology, which is considered in the article is e-learning. The letter “e” in e-learning stands for “electronic”, so e-learning can be defined as the education without using paper printed tools or instructional materials [11]. Another definitions for e-learning are “E-learning is the learning supported by digital electronic tools and media” and “E-learning covers a wide set of applications and processes, including multimedia online activities such as the web, Internet video SD-ROM, TV and radio. Students can use these materials to teach themselves” [5]. With the help of e-learning, participants in the educational process connected to the Internet have access to learning at any time and in any places. Benefits of e-learning might be crucial for both teachers and students, also during the trend for lifelong learning e-learning replaces traditional classroom learning for people who work full-time and give opportunity to acquire new language or new skill. Moreover, e-learning has been implemented into education of different countries, there is to say that both teachers and students are already familiar with e-learning at different levels and use it in everyday practice.

In Kazakhstan, the project “E-learning System” was launched by the Ministry of Education and Science in 2011. According to the National Center for Informatization in 2011, “The main goal of e-learning in the system of higher professional education is to expand access to basic knowledge”[4]. Considering that

many Kazakhstani universities have implemented e-learning platforms based on Moodle or developed by university staff, education has become available, and during and after quarantine, students were given the opportunity to continue their studies remotely. Thus, the advantages of e-learning in education are in the effectiveness and development of self-realization competencies of students in all periods of their lives. In addition to this, since the distinctive features of modern higher education are flexibility, efficiency and practice-oriented learning, such knowledge exchange marks the transition from the reproductive traditional transfer of knowledge to a creative form of learning with its innovative methods, forms, resources.

The second application of ICT which considered is mobile learning used as creative form of teaching or learning, and known as in education field of smart education. M-learning is the "e-learning using mobile devices and wireless transmission" [5]. The letter "m" in m-learning stands for the word "mobile", and consequently there might arise two definitions. The first is m-learning is learning using mobile devices, precisely using smartphones (mobile phones, cell phones), tablets and the second definition m-learning is mobility of learning, for example, learning while commuting, travelling and etc. There is to say that both definitions are correct, mobile phones are comfortable for using while travelling, commuting and even walking and learning especially from different apps in foreign language learning or different courses and skills might be easily available due to mobile phone which is main tool of "mobile learning".

E-learning and mobile learning are closely related. According to Behera (2013), m-learning is considered an extension of e-learning, but the quality of m-learning can be ensured taking into account the special limitations and advantages of mobile devices. However, despite the close connection, they have some differences, therefore, in teaching a foreign language, or when learning a foreign language independently, one or another type of online learning may be preferred.

Methods

In the 21st century technology made a breakthrough and not only originated new specialties, but also different terms. Since in this article examination occurs in the field of education, it is necessary to identify the level of proficiency and frequency of use of the above-mentioned types of online learning by teachers and students. For example, what are the differences between e-learning, m-learning, d-learning, if the principle of learning is based on using a device connected to the internet.

The method of research is descriptive-survey in order to collect answers on current theme using survey as instrument of research. The research data were obtained using an electronic survey on the knowledge of

the differences between electronic and mobile learning, readiness and use of new technologies in teaching, what advantages electronic and mobile learning has among teachers and students. The data were analyzed using the percentage of students' responses to a given questionnaire.

The study consisted of questions divided into two parts. Undergraduate and graduate students and teachers participated in the surveys. The numbers of people surveyed are fifteen. The first part is a knowledge test of the types of online learning, how ready students/teachers are for e-learning with indicators of understanding the Internet, searching the Internet (educational resources, e-books), comprehend e-learning and m-learning, the ability to use various computer applications, the availability of a network during quarantine in the country, difficulties to get in touch in distance learning, and whether students have a laptop and the Internet, which devices students use (laptop, smartphone, personal computer or public libraries with access to computers connected to the Internet).

The second part examines such aspects as the benefits and difficulties, wide usage of electronic and mobile learning in teaching and learning foreign languages. It should be noted that the training based on the achievements of information technology has a number of undeniable advantages, including the absence of the problem of geographical remoteness, lower transport costs, accommodation for students and teachers in remote regions. In addition to this, flexibility is also an advantage of online learning, students can independently choose the time to study courses available on the Internet; connect to the learning process from anywhere; certified specialists have the opportunity to develop new necessary professional skills in the learning process throughout their lives. The use of electronic libraries, the opportunity to familiarize students with the full course of study, the opportunity to add additional materials to the e-learning platform, the use of mobile applications for learning foreign languages as a way of additional material to the basic training.

On the other hand, electronic and mobile learning have a number of disadvantages. The lack of control of students leads to a loss of discipline. Not all students will be able to independently understand the materials provided by the teacher in electronic platforms. The unreliability of materials from the Internet leads to a decrease in the understanding of the logical connections of topics, the lack of a sense of the learning process, the inability to ask questions directly if there is a misunderstanding of the material.

Results of the research and discussion

The data obtained using the first part of the question about students' and teachers' knowledge of electronic and mobile learning shown using pie chart and percentages.

Figure 1. Understanding and using e-learning and mobile learning.

While m-learning uses the terminology as "mobile", not only mobile phones are used here, but the main goal is the mobility of learning, some complications in understanding the differences in online learning terms were expected from the survey participants. According to the pie chart, 80% of students/teachers understand the differences between types of online learning, more precisely, types such as e-learning and m-learning. Moreover, these percentages show that students actively use the university's platform, mainly based on MOODLE implemented by their universities. Another 20% of students and teachers experience minor difficulties due to differences in the types of online learning. The pie chart shows that 20% of students and teachers prefer the traditional way of teaching to e-learning and m-learning. According to 20% of respondents, the use of traditional methods, paper books gives greater efficiency and are less harmful to health. In addition to this, teaching with the help of electronic resources, multimedia, mobile applications does not have a systematic approach and is more suitable for self-study of the language.

Figure 1 shows that the people who were interviewed in the first part use e-learning in teaching, a great advantage for evaluating students who could not attend class, have health problems, namely 80% of teachers actively use e-learning and mobile learning in teaching. According to Geist (2011), through the m-learning, students can easily buy e-books and they can download to their devices [5]. The students evaluated the effectiveness of e-learning for self-preparation at home, additional materials like e-books, e-library helps to study without leaving home. According to the survey, 80% of teachers and students actively use e-learning, as it is implemented by the university, and has great efficiency. The advantages of e-learning and mobile learning include training that can be conducted anywhere and anytime, e-learning makes the learning process regular, e-learning costs are cheaper, materials are easily accessible.

The data on the use of various applications, mobile learning and e-learning obtained from the questionnaire can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows that teachers and students widely use e-learning and mobile learning when learning or teaching a foreign language, namely, 34% of teachers

use electronic portals to interact with students, e-books to get additional material to the topic, videos with vari-

ous educational contents as additional material for students. It can be noted that the percentage of using mobile and e-learning in the practice of teaching a foreign language is quite good, but very limited. A big disadvantage for teachers is the lack of direct communication between the teacher and the student, which affects the discipline and motivation of students for the worse. Therefore, many teachers, despite the great effectiveness of electronic and mobile learning, combine them with the great advantage of using traditional teaching methods.

Students have an indicator of 66%, independent study of a foreign language using mobile applications such as "Cake", "Duolingo", etc. It is accessible for students to assimilate electronic materials, learn a foreign language through webinars, films, websites, educational portals, games and applications. Students prefer the transition from the reproductive traditional transfer of knowledge to a creative form of learning with innovative methods, forms, and means.

The survey results show that against the background of the massive use of online technologies during the pandemic, the successful introduction of e-learning in Kazakhstan and other factors, the level of knowledge of teachers and students about various types of online learning is 80%, and this is considered as a good indicator. According to the second survey, students use mobile and electronic learning more than teachers. This can be explained by the fact that in the modern world of technology, students tend to self-educate, materials based on a book may be insufficient, sometimes boring, and the use of online learning, smart technology in learning a foreign language makes it possible to immerse yourself in the environment of a foreign language. It cannot be said that teachers do not know how or refuse to use various types of online learning in teaching a foreign language at all, many teachers agree with the advantage of using online learning, as an example to this, let us cite Mustari A., Viharto M. (2019), which state that the benefits of e-learning include speeding up work, improving efficiency, improving productivity, increasing productivity and efficiency, and making work easier[7]. But computer technology will not replace teachers, combining the traditional method of teaching and smart education can also be effective for students.

Conclusion

The economy and technology rapidly develop on a global scale, the increasing of international tourism around the world have caused the continued expansion of learning foreign languages. The reasons for learning a new language are many, but the importance of learning foreign languages is universal that is it will always benefit you in one way or another. The article substantiates the need to use SMART technologies in teaching a foreign language(s), formulates the basic principles of their functioning and the main characteristics. Using the example of SMART technology tools (webinars, social networks, blogs, an e-learning system, and SMART textbooks, moodle), the author analyzes the relevance and validity of their use from both didactic and technological point of views, focuses on the need for continuous improvement of the learning process

with their help. It is important to mention that acquiring foreign languages also have become accessible with different apps such as Cake, Duolingo, hellotalk etc. which have been created to improve different skills (some focused on writing, some only teach language by videos) although, all of them (apps for learning languages) can make learning uncomplicated and engaging despite the fact that they cannot used frequently in traditional learning.

In this article also mentions benefits of using apps written above for self-education or teaching outside the classroom. Eventually, using smart (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, time-bound) technologies such as smartphones, e-learning, m-learning, d-learning, e-gadgets in foreign language teaching can assist students enhance knowledge not only in languages but also in IT technologies which lead us to the term of integration. The process of integration of different areas is now developing, sciences as language and technology seemed in the past as sciences impossible to merge into one science, nowadays declare that can play an important role and help each other achieve certain goals. Therefore modern language teaching is often associates as teaching using various technologies, because even the word "modern" is interpreted as a person who knows and uses new technologies.

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